

Quantum Mechanics and Writing the LHS of $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ in terms of a Gradient?

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In (1), it is argued that the Schrodinger (nonrelativistic) quantum equation may be developed from steady state type classical equations linked to the continuity equation and Newton's second law. Given the nonrelativistic treatment of (1), $F=dp/dt = d/dt (mv) = m dv/dt + mv dv/dx$. In (1) an equation (III.2) for many particles is obtained from the equation for a single particle:

$$M d (dv/dt + v \cdot \text{grad } v) = dF + \hbar/4m \text{grad} \cdot (\text{grad grad } d - 1/d (\text{grad } d) (\text{grad } d)).$$

In (1), it is further assumed that $v = \text{grad } (\phi)$ for conservative forces, where ϕ is a function of x,t . One may then see that for $d=1$ case, for a single particle, that $\phi = -Et + px$ and that one may write a Schrodinger equation which is essentially a conservation of energy equation.

Here, we consider starting with $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ and using a special relativistic treatment. We note that for a conservative force, $F = -\text{grad } V$ and suggest trying to write the LHS in terms of a gradient for a free particle so the gradient may be "pulled out" from both sides of $dp/dt = F$. From a physical point of view, F is a pull or push, but we argue that V (potential) is also physical and that given that p is almost like a force, that there should be meaning to $p = \text{grad } \phi(x,t)$. This is the basis premise.

In the case, $F=0$, we show that one may obtain $-E^2 + p \cdot p = \text{constant}$ via this approach which involves writing $p = d/dx (-Et + px)$ (one dimension). We note that associating $dp/dt = F$ with a Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ shows the close association of Newton's second law with special relativity because $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ is relativistic as long as $p = mv/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. We suggest that this approach associates operators d/dt and $-i \text{grad}$ ($\hbar=1$) with E and p and allows one to write a free particle equation (Klein-Gordon) in terms of $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$, which is a quantum form. We suggest that one way in which to see free particle quantum mechanics emerge (albeit in the simplest case-that of a free relativistic particle) is to try to consider dp/dt in terms of a gradient suggesting that there may be x, t features even for E, p constant. In Newtonian mechanics, a constant E and p immediately implies that derivatives are 0. This need not be the case if one considers $p = d/dx (-Et + px)$. The legitimacy of considering p (which is closely linked to a force) is linked to the legitimacy of considering $F = -\text{grad } V$. In other words, V is a potential which is another way of considering the features of a force and $p = d/dx (-Et + px)$ may mean that $-Et + px$ (and $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$) may be another way of considering p, E at a deeper level than simply stating that one has a constant E, p for a free particle. We argue that one does not need to consider a continuity equation as done in (1) and that the full approach follows from analysis of a single free particle (constant E, p) in the special relativistic case, which then yields also the nonrelativistic one.

Approach of (1)

In (1), a steady state density-Newton's second law nonrelativistic approach is taken towards obtaining the Schrodinger equation. Although we ultimately wish to consider a relativistic case for a free particle (constant density), we first briefly present the ideas of (1).

The starting point seems to be the single particle equation:

$$m d \left(\frac{dv}{dt} \text{partial} + v \text{ dot grad } v \right) = dF + \hbar^2 / 4m \text{ grad dot (grad grad } d - 1/d (\text{grad } d) (\text{grad } d)) \quad ((1))$$

where d is density, F is force and v is velocity. One may note that:

$\frac{dv}{dt} \text{partial} + v \text{ dot grad } v = F$ is Newton's second law ((2)) albeit for a velocity field type situation.

In (1), ((1)) is summed over K particles, but a key feature is to introduce:

$$v = \text{grad } \phi(x,t) \quad ((3))$$

for a conservative force, i.e. one for which $F = -\text{grad } V$, where V is the potential.

If one considers ((2)), then

$$d \text{ grad } \phi + \frac{1}{2} \text{ grad } \{ \text{grad } \phi \text{ dot grad } \phi \} = -\text{grad } V \quad ((4))$$

One may interchange grad and $d \text{ grad}$ and then "pull out" the grad yielding:

$$d \text{ grad } \phi + \frac{1}{2} \text{ grad } \phi \text{ dot grad } \phi = -V \quad ((5))$$

((5)) has the appearance of the usual conservation equation suggesting that:

$$\phi = -KE t + v m x \quad ((6))$$

Although this approach is nonrelativistic and introduces $v = \text{grad } \phi$ based on a conservative force, we suggest that it may be generalized to the relativistic case and that the notion of writing v in terms of a grad should be discussed in further detail.

We note that ((5)) is a conservation law which uses operators $d \text{ grad}$ and grad acting on ϕ ((6)) to obtain a conservation equation. As noted in ((1)), one may also create a similar Schrodinger equation in which one uses $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, i.e.

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(-iEt+ipx) + V(x) \exp(-iEt+ipx) = i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((7))$$

To solve ((4)), all that is needed is that $\phi = -KE + mv x$, but overall, the more general equation ((1)) exists and to solve this, one uses:

$$d \exp(-i \phi) \quad ((8)) \text{ where } d \text{ is spatial density.}$$

Thus, ϕ is linked with Newton's second law and d , with steady state density considerations. If one has a single particle then one may consider only Newton's second law features and use $d=1$. One may note that density features partially appear in (1) through:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} d + \text{grad} \cdot (v d) = 0 \quad \text{continuity equation} \quad ((8))$$

We suggest that one may consider a theory for a single particle and use $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ to create a probability which leads to density through $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, we wish to create a relativistic theory.

F=dp/dt, Special Relativity and a Single Particle Leading to Quantum Mechanics

We wish to create a relativistic description of a single particle with constant E, p which is based on the notion of Newton's second law $dp/dt = F$ and the idea that if F is linked to $-\text{grad} V$, then p should also be linked to a gradient because physically p (momentum) is very similar to a force. Furthermore, this approach is associated with steady state behaviour in t, x and not the deterministic $x(t)$ Newtonian one.

As a result, we consider:

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{dp}{dt} \text{partial} + v \frac{dp}{dx} = 0 \quad (\text{one dimension}) \quad ((9))$$

We note that the form ((9)) implies a steady state view because for $p = \text{constant}$, $dp/dt = 0$ and so one would not break up dp/dt as done in ((9)). This suggests that one is moving away from a Newtonian $x(t)$ deterministic description. Given that this is the case, one should try to define exactly the kind of steady state approach considered. We argue that the driving idea is to consider p in terms of gradient $\phi(x, t)$ because a conservative force $F = -\text{grad} V$. In other words, F may be associated with a potential and we argue that because p physically behaves almost as a force by crashing into targets, that one should be able to link p with a $\text{grad} \phi(x, t)$. We know that $F = dp/dt$ is strongly linked to special relativity (as it holds relativistically for $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$), so we consider:

$$\phi = -Et+px \quad \text{where } E = mocc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ and } p = mov/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((10))$$

Then ((9)) becomes:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dx} (-Et+px) + v \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (-Et+px) = 0 \quad ((10))$$

One may multiply by E and use $E v = p$ for $c=1$. Then:

$$d/dx \{ -E^2 + p^2 \} = 0 \text{ or } -EE + pp = \text{constant} \quad ((11))$$

((11)) is the Lorentz invariant: $-EE + pp = -m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) ((12))

In order to fully create a steady state picture, one should have a probability in space for the free particle given by:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((13))$$

This is linked to the operators $i\partial/\partial t$ for E and $-i\text{grad}$ for p. Furthermore, ((13)) provides for conservation of energy and momentum as:

$$p(E_1, p_1) p(E_2, p_2) = p(E_1+E_2, p_1+p_2) \quad ((14))$$

Given the special relativistic form ((13)), one may show that the same ideas hold for the nonrelativistic case:

$$dp/dt = dp/dt \text{ partial} + v dp/dx = 0 \text{ with } p=mv \text{ so:}$$

$$dp/dt \text{ partial} + .5/m_0 d/dx p^2 = 0 \quad \text{and using } \phi = -KE t + p x \text{ one obtains:}$$

$$\text{grad} \{ -KE + 1/2m p^2 \} = 0 \text{ or } KE = p^2/2m \quad ((15))$$

It is interesting to note that one introduces $p = \text{grad} (-KE t + px)$ because $dp/dt \text{ partial}$ must yield energy. It seems that one is using the idea of 4-vectors in $dp/dt = F$ (Newton's second law).

The basic idea present seems to be that given $dp/dt = F$ and $F = -\text{grad} V$ for a conservative force, that there seems to be some underlying physics linked to F, namely the potential V. We argue that the potential is not merely a math construct. It is already known that F is physical because it is associated with a push or pull, but now there is a second function $V(x)$ which we argue is also physical. We then suggest that there should be a corresponding field or steady stream linked with p, which we argue may be written as $\text{grad} \phi$ because p is almost like a force. This leads to $p = d/dx (-Et+px)$ and we then generalize to the probability (steady stream or probability field) $\exp(-Et+ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that because a conservative force F (which is a physical push or pull) may be written as $-\text{Grad} V$, that $V(x)$ has physical meaning as well, and is not simply a math function. If this is the case, we argue that Newton's second $dp/dt = F$ suggests that perhaps p may also be written as $\text{grad} \phi(x,t)$ as p is almost like a force. This immediately leads to a steady state view because for a free particle with constant p, $dp/dt=0$ and one would not

consider a $\phi(x,t)$. The idea for special relativity is that one may write $dp/dt = dp/dt \text{ partial} + v dp/dx = 0$ (one dimension). This is a field/steady stream type approach because for p constant, $dp/dt=0$ and one would not write dp/dx . One may then multiply by E because $Ev = p$ for $c=1$. If one uses $\phi = -Et+px$ (a Lorentz invariant), this leads to: $\text{grad} (-EE + pp) = 0$ and one may pull out grad to obtain $-EE+pp = \text{constant}$ (i.e. -momo). To create the steady stream picture, we consider $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as a probability which conserves energy and momentum and use $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-i\text{grad}$ partial as operators which yield E,p . As a result, free particle quantum mechanics arises from this approach.

References

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